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Review Paper

Nardostachys jatamansi DC: From Ayurvedic Heritage to Modern Pharmacognostic and Pharmacological Validation

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ABSTRACT

Nardostachys jatamansi DC. (Valerianaceae), commonly known as Jatamansi, is an important medicinal plant widely employed in traditional systems of medicine, especially Ayurveda, for the treatment of neurological, psychological, and systemic disorders. Owing to its broad therapeutic potential and diverse phytochemical composition, the plant has attracted considerable scientific attention in recent years. The present review provides a comprehensive and critical evaluation of existing literature on N. jatamansi, encompassing its historical significance, taxonomical classification, geographical distribution and detailed macroscopic and microscopic characteristics along with its Ayurvedic properties. Traditional medicinal uses, physicochemical parameters and phytochemical screening are systematically discussed to establish quality and identity standards. Special emphasis is placed on the plant's phytochemistry, highlighting major bioactive constituents and their chemical structures. Additionally, the review summarizes experimental evidence supporting a wide range of pharmacological activities, including neuroprotective, antioxidant, hepatoprotective, antimicrobial, anxiolytic and anti-inflammatory effects. Acute toxicity studies and the role of N. jatamansi in various polyherbal formulations are examined to assess its safety and therapeutic applicability. Furthermore, biotechnological strategies aimed at the conservation and sustainable utilization of this endangered medicinal plant is reviewed. Overall, this article consolidates scientific evidence validating the traditional uses of N.jatamansi and underscores its potential for future research and herbal drug development.

INTRODUCTION

Role of Herbal Medicine

Herbal medicines derived from natural and medicinal plants possess considerable potential in pharmaceutical, cosmetic and modern therapeutic

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applications. Compared to synthetic chemical drugs, plant-based medicines generally exhibit fewer adverse effects and better patient tolerance. Many chemical medications, composed largely of synthetic compounds, are often associated with undesirable side effects. Consequently, herbal remedies have been traditionally and extensively used as safer alternatives to chemical drugs [1]. Herbal medicines are also referred to as phytomedicines, phytopharmaceuticals, phytotherapeutic agents, herbal products or herbal remedies. Phytotherapy is defined as the scientifically validated use of medicinal plants for the prevention and treatment of diseases. In contrast, traditional herbalism relies on the holistic application of herbal remedies based primarily on empirical knowledge and long-standing traditional practices rather than scientific validation [2].

N.jatamansi DC is a compact, long-lived, rhizome-bearing plant that grows on steep, damp, rocky and undisturbed grassy slopes of India, Nepal, China and Bhutan [3]. It possesses significant historical importance in Ayurveda, Homeopathy, traditional healing systems and the Indian System of Medicine (ISM) and continues to be used in the modern pharmaceutical industry for its medicinal value. It is considered one of the earliest known species of the Valerianaceae family [4]. The plant has a long-established historical background, with the term *Valeriana* first documented in medicinal texts of the 9th and 10th centuries. *N.jatamansi* has been highly valued for its therapeutic properties in Ayurveda in India, Unani medicine of ancient Greek and Arab traditions, as well as in the medical systems of ancient Egypt and Rome. The root powder is mentioned in certain Islamic traditions as the forbidden fruit consumed by Adam in Paradise. During medieval times in Europe, it was an important component of spice blends used for culinary seasoning, and Hippocrates incorporated it into a sweetened, spiced wine preparation. In

Ayurveda, the rhizomes are used as a bitter tonic, stimulant, antispasmodic and have traditionally been employed in the management of epilepsy and hysteria^[5, 6, 7].

N. jatamansi has been used in the treatment of various ailments and exhibits multiple pharmacological activities, including anticonvulsant, anti-Parkinsonian, sedative, hepatoprotective, neuroprotective, antihypertensive and antidiabetic effects [8]. It is also reported to be beneficial in disorders of the digestive, circulatory, urinary and reproductive systems, as well as in various skin diseases.

HISTORY

The term *Valeriana* first appeared in literary records dating back to the 9th and 10th centuries. Since ancient times, the plant has been highly regarded for its therapeutic importance across multiple traditional medical systems, including Ayurveda in India, Unani medicine rooted in Greek and Arab traditions, as well as in ancient Egypt and Rome. In certain Islamic narrations, the powdered root of *N. jatamansi* is symbolically associated with the fruit consumed by Adam in Paradise, which was prohibited by God. During the medieval period in Europe, the plant was also employed as a culinary additive, particularly in spice mixtures used for flavouring foods. In Ayurveda, the rhizomes of *N. jatamansi* are traditionally utilized as a bitter tonic and stimulant and are prescribed for their antispasmodic properties as well as in the management of epilepsy and hysteria.^[9, 10, 11]

TAXONOMICAL CLASSIFICATION [12, 13]:

Kingdom	Plantae
Division	Magnoliophyta
Class	Magnoliopsida
Order	Dipsacales
Family	Valerianaceae
Genus	Nardostachys
Species	jatamansi

Vernacular Names of *N. jatamansi* ^[14,15,16]

Language/ region	Names used
Arabic	Sumbul-ul-Asfar, Sumbul-ul-Hind, Sumbul-ut-Tibbeh-Hindi
Assamese	Jatamansi, Jatamangshi
Bengali	Jatamasi, Kalichad, Balchad
English	Spikenard, Indian Nard, Musk Root, Nardus Root
Hindi	Jatamansi, Balchar, Balchir, Baluchar, Jatalasi
Kannada	Jatamamsi, Jatamavsi, Bhootajata, Ganagila Maste
Kashmiri	Bhutijata, Bhut-Jati, Kukil-i-Pot
Malayalam	Jatamanchi, Jetamanshi, Manchi
Marathi	Jatamansi, Jatamashi, Balchhar
(Oriya)	Jatamansi
Persian	Sumbulat, Sunbul-ut-Tih
Tamil Odia	Jatamansi, Jatamanji
Telugu	Jatamamsi, Jatamsi, Jatam-Imshi
Urdu	Balachhada, Sambul-ut-Teeb

Synonym: Mansi, Kiratinini, Krishanjata, Krvyadi, Jatila, Bhootjata, Tpasvini Nalda, Plankha.

Geographical Distribution: ^[21,22] The plant is found in the Alpine Himalayas at high altitudes (3,000–5,000 m) and is distributed Eastwards from Kumaon up to Bhutan and Sikkim.

Habit: The plant possesses a thick, woody rootstock that is elongated and robust and it is densely covered with fibrous remains of dried leaf petioles.

Flowering and Fruiting Period: The plant flowers and bears fruit from the rainy season through the autumn months

MICROSCOPIC CHARACTER ^[19]

A transverse section of the rhizome reveals a thin periderm and a broad parenchymatous cortex rich in starch grains. The endodermis contains globules of volatile oil. A ring of collateral vascular bundles encloses a large central pith, within which scattered groups of sclerenchymatous cells are present.

MACROSCOPIC CHARACTER ^[17, 18]

JATAMANSI

Stem: The stem attains a height of about 10–60 cm, shows pubescence toward the upper portion, becomes nearly smooth at the base and is generally subscapose in nature.

Leaves: Basal leaves measure approximately 15–20 cm in length and about 2.5 cm in width, exhibit prominent longitudinal venation and are spatulate in shape with an elongated form. Stem leaves are sessile, either glabrous or slightly hairy and taper gradually into the petiole.

Flowers: The flowers are arranged in cymose heads, commonly appearing singly or in groups of 3 to 5. They are rosy to pale pink or bluish in colour, accompanied by oblong bracts of about 6 mm in length, which are usually pubescent.

Corolla: The corolla tube is nearly 6 mm long and bears slight internal hairs; the filaments are also hairy near the base.

Fruit: The fruit measures around 4 mm in length and is covered with upward-directed white hairs. It is topped by an ovate, acute calyx with frequently toothed margins

AYURVEDIC PROPERTIES ^[20]

Rasa [taste]-Tikta, Kashaya	Guna
[qualities]-Laghu	
Virya [potency]-sheetha	Prabhava-
Bootagna	
Dashaghnta-Tridoshashamaka	

TRADITIONAL USES ^[23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28]

S. No	Traditional Use	Description
1	Sannipatikavikara	A condition arising from the imbalance of 3 doshas (Vata, Pitta, Kapha) causing various systemic disorders.
2	Vatavyadhi	Disorders related to Vata dosha, often manifesting as pain, dryness and neurological issues.
3	Shotha	Swelling or inflammation of tissues, particularly as seen in conditions like arthritis or infections.
4	Unmada	Mental disorders or madness characterized by disturbances in the mind and senses.
5	Murchha	Fainting or a state of unconsciousness often due to a sudden drop in blood pressure or intense stress.

6	Chitodvega	Disturbance of the mind marked by anxiety, excitement, or agitation.
7	Manasavikara	Psychological disorders including anxiety, depression or other mental health issues.
8	Vismriti	Memory loss or forgetfulness often due to mental fatigue or stress.
9	Shoola	Abdominal pain or discomfort can also refer to other types of pain in the body.
10	Daha	Burning sensations within the body, particularly in conditions related to Pitta dosha.
11	Visphota	Conditions characterized by bursting pains, often related to accumulation of gas or digestive issues.
12	Vranashotha	Inflammation associated with wounds or ulcers, promoting healing.
13	Varnavikara	Skin disorders affecting pigmentation or coloration.
14	Swedadhikya	Excessive sweating which could be symptomatic of various underlying conditions.
15	Sweda-daurgandhya	Foul-smelling sweat, often linked to metabolic or digestive imbalances.
16	Apasmara	Epilepsy or disorders marked by sudden seizures or temporary loss of consciousness.
17	Apatantraka	Mobility issues related to muscle weakness or rigidity.
18	Mastishka daurbalya	Weakness of the brain or nervous system, leading to fatigue and cognitive decline.
19	Shirahshoola	Headaches or migraines that can be debilitating.
20	Kampavata	Conditions involving tremors or spasms, often seen in Parkinson's disease or essential tremor.
21	Nidranasha	Insomnia or lack of sleep that affects overall health and well-being.
22	Agnimandya	Reduced digestive fire, leading to poor digestion and metabolic issues.
23	Anaha	Abdominal distension or bloating often due to gas retention.
24	Udarashoola	Severe abdominal pain or discomfort related to digestive issues or gastritis.
25	Amashayashotha	Inflammation of the stomach, which can lead to discomfort and digestive disturbances.
26	Chhardi	Nausea or vomiting, often signalling gastrointestinal disturbances.
27	Kamala	Jaundice or liver dysfunction, often signified by yellowing of the skin and eyes.
28	Hridrava	Cardiac weakness or conditions relating to heart health.
29	Raktabharadhikya	Conditions characterized by excessive blood circulation or disorders leading to bleeding tendencies.
30	Arsha	Haemorrhoids or anal fissures that can cause pain and discomfort.
31	Hikka	Hiccups or spasms of the diaphragm, often indicating irritability in the gastrointestinal tract.
32	Kasa	Cough, which can be acute or chronic, often related to respiratory health.

33	Shwasa	Asthma or difficulty in breathing characterized by wheezing and respiratory distress.
34	Mootrakrichehbra	Difficult or painful urination, often due to urinary tract issues.
35	Bastishotha	Inflammation of the urinary bladder, leading to pain and discomfort.
36	Klaibya	Impotence or sexual dysfunction affecting male reproductive health.
37	Piditartava	Disorders affecting menstruation, which may include pain or irregularities.
38	Sadyovrana	Fresh or acute wounds that require prompt healing.
39	Bhagna	Fractures that need attention for healing and recovery.
40	Garbhashaya shotha	Inflammation of the uterus, which may lead to various gynaecological issues.
41	Twagvikara	Skin diseases or disorders affecting the skin's health and appearance.
42	Vatarakta	Gout or conditions resulting from an imbalance of Vata and blood disorders.
43	Visarpa	Skin diseases characterized by inflammatory lesions, often resembling serpiginous patterns.
44	Daurbalya	General weakness or debility that affects various bodily functions.
45	Sannipatika jwara	Fever arising from the imbalance of all three doshas, indicating systemic issues.
46	Raktaprakopa	Conditions marked by excessive blood heat or irritability leading to various health problems.
47	Bhrama	Dizziness or vertigo often resulting from disturbances in the inner ear or balance.
48	Dantashoola	Toothache, which can arise from dental issues or infections.
49	Mukharoga	Oral diseases including infections or irritations affecting oral health.
50	Mukhadaurgandhya	Bad breath or foul odour emerging from the mouth, which may signal oral or digestive issues.
51	Netraroga	Eye disorders or conditions affecting vision and eye health.
52	Vishavikara	Poisoning or illnesses caused by toxic substances, requiring detoxification.
53	Ashmari	Kidney stones or urinary calculi, leading to pain and urinary issues.
54	Kushtha	Chronic skin diseases, including leprosy or other similar conditions.
55	Bhootabadha	Conditions believed to be caused by evil spirits or negative energies.

PHYSICO CHEMICAL PROPERTIES ^[29]

Determination of Total Phenolic Content

The total phenolic content was found to be **53.06 ± 2.2 mg GAE/g** in the ethanolic extract and **13.87 ± 1.3 mg GAE/g** in the hexane extract of *N. jatamansi*.

Total Flavonoid Content

The flavonoid content was estimated as **25.303 ± 0.9 mg CE/g** for the ethanolic extract and **4.58 ± 0.3 mg CE/g** for the hexane extract of *N. jatamansi*.

Physico-chemical properties

- **Specific gravity:** ranges from 0.9300 to 0.9587 at 25 °C
- **Refractive index:** ranges between 1.5055 and 1.5458 at 25 °C
- **Acid number:** 1.5 to 8
- **Ester number:** 6 to 45
- **Ester number after acetylation:** 40 to 65
- **Solubility:** soluble in 0.4 to 1.5 volumes of 90% alcohol

PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING ^[30]

Phytochemical screening was carried out to determine the presence or absence of various phytoconstituents in the distilled water and methanolic extracts of *N. jatamansi*.^[23]

Test for Carbohydrates

Fehling' s test:

Equal volumes (1 ml each) of Fehling's solutions A and B were mixed, followed by the addition of 0.5 mL of the extract. The mixture was boiled for a few minutes. Formation of a brick-red precipitate indicated the presence of reducing sugars.

Benedict's test:

About 1 ml of Benedict's reagent was added to the plant extract and boiled. The appearance of a reddish-brown precipitate confirmed the presence of carbohydrates.

Molisch's test:

Approximately 1 ml of Molisch's reagent was added to the plant extract and mixed thoroughly. Concentrated sulfuric acid (1 ml) was carefully added along the sides of the test tube. Formation of a violet ring at the junction indicated the presence of carbohydrates.

Iodine test:

About 1 ml of iodine solution was added to the plant extract. The development of a dark blue or

purple colour indicated the presence of carbohydrates.

Test for Proteins and Amino acids

Millon's test:

1ml of Millon's reagent was added to the plant extract, producing a white precipitate. Upon heating, the precipitate turned red, indicating the presence of proteins.

Ninhydrin test:

The plant extract was mixed with 1 ml of Ninhydrin solution and boiled. The appearance of a violet colour confirmed the presence of amino acids and proteins.

Test for Glycosides

Salkowski's test:

1 ml of chloroform was mixed with the plant extract, followed by the addition of 0.5 mL of concentrated sulfuric acid. The formation of a reddish-brown coloration indicated the presence of glycosides.

Test for Steroids

The plant extract was mixed with 1 ml of chloroform, and 0.5 ml of concentrated sulfuric acid was carefully added along the sides of the test tube. The appearance of a red colour in the chloroform layer indicated the presence of steroids.

Test for Alkaloids

The plant extract was treated with 0.5 ml of hydrochloric acid and gently heated. Equal amounts of Mayer's and Wagner's reagents were then added. Formation of turbidity or precipitate confirmed the presence of alkaloids.

Test for Phenols

A lead acetate test was performed by adding 1 ml of ferric chloride solution to the plant extract. The appearance of a blue-green or black coloration indicated the presence of phenolic compounds.

Test for tannins

The plant extract was dissolved in 1 ml of distilled water, and 1–2 drops of ferric chloride solution were added. The development of a blue or green colour indicated the presence of tannins.

Test for Flavonoids

A magnesium ribbon followed by concentrated hydrochloric acid was added to the plant extract. The appearance of a pink or scarlet coloration within 1–2 min indicated the presence of flavonoids.

Test for Terpenoids

The plant extract was dissolved in 1 ml of chloroform and concentrated sulphuric acid is added along the side of the test tube. A reddish brown coloration appears at the interface. This indicates the presence of terpenoids.

PHYTO-CHEMISTRY^[31,32,33,34]

The rhizomes and roots of *N. jatamansi* possess significant medicinal importance and have therefore been extensively investigated for their chemical constituents. Chatterjee *et al.* carried out a detailed chemical analysis of the rhizomes, resulting in the isolation of a novel terpenoid ester, nardo-stachysin. The plant has been reported to contain both volatile and non-volatile phytochemicals. Sesquiterpenes constitute the major fraction of the volatile components, whereas sesquiterpenes, coumarins, lignans, neolignans, and alkaloids predominate in the non-volatile extracts. Sesquiterpenes and coumarins occur in considerable quantities in the roots of jatamansi and are chiefly responsible for its essential oil content.

Chemical Constituents of *N. jatamansi*

- Rich in sesquiterpenes and sesquiterpene derivatives
- **Major constituents include:**
 - α -Patchoulene
 - β -Patchoulene
 - β -Eudesmol
 - Angelicin
 - Valeranal
 - Valeranone
 - Patchouli alcohol
 - Seychellene
 - Seychelane
 - Elemol
 - Calarene
 - Calarenol
 - Nardol
 - Nardostachone
 - Nardostechone
 - Norsechelanone
- **Jatamansi-specific compounds:**
 - Jatamansin
 - Jatamansinol
 - Jatamansone
 - Jatamansinone
 - Dihydrojatamansin
 - Spirojatamol
 - Jatamol A and B
 - Jatamansic acid
- **Other sesquiterpenes reported:**
 - Nardin
 - Nardal (*pharmacologically active component*)
 - Nardostachyin
 - Nardosinone
 - Seselin
 - Oroselol
 - Oroseolol
 - Oroselone
- **Sterols and hydrocarbons:**
 - β -Sitosterol
 - n-Hexacosane

- n-Hexacosanol
- **Esters:**
- n-Hexacosanyl arachidate
- n-Hexacosanyl isovalerate
- **Other constituents:**
- Volatile essential oil
- Resins
- Gums
- Sugars
- Starch
- Bitter extractive matter
- Ketones
- Sesquiterpene ketones
- **Coumarin:**
- Xanthogalin
- **Alkaloid:**
- Actinidine

Chemical structures

Actinidine

Aristolene

Beta sitosterol

Beta-patchoulene

Angelecin

Jatamansone

MULTI HERBAL FORMULATION OF JATAMANSI

Incorporation and use of Jatamansi

Jatamansi can be utilized in various forms depending on the intended therapeutic purpose.

1. As a tea or infusion:
The root powder of Jatamansi may be steeped in hot water to prepare a tea or infusion. This method is traditionally employed to promote relaxation, relieve stress and support mental calmness.

2. As an essential oil: Jatamansi essential oil is widely used in aromatherapy. A few drops may be added to a diffuser or inhaled directly for its soothing effects. When diluted with carrier oils such as coconut or jojoba oil, it can also be applied for massage therapy or skin care purposes.
3. In capsule or tablet form: Standardized extracts of Jatamansi are available as capsules or tablets, offering a convenient option for oral administration. These formulations are commonly used as dietary supplements or incorporated into therapeutic regimens under professional guidance.
4. As a powder: Jatamansi powder can be mixed with food or beverages or applied externally as part of herbal preparations for hair and skin care

Herbal products	Type of product	Medicinal uses of the products	Manufacturing company
Anxocare	Tablet	To remove anxiety	The Himalaya Drug Company
Aruna	Syrup	Premenopausal symptoms	Ayurvedashramam
B pex	Capsule	To treat cardiac neurosis and anxiety diseases	Jeevanrekha company
Brahmos	Capsule	To treat anxiety and depression	Jeevanrekha company
Chaitanya	Capsule	To improve immunity and get rid of fatigue	Dindaya Industries Ltd. Gwalior
Eve Plus	Tablet	To regulate menstrual cycle	Megha Pharmaceuticals
Gro HR	Tablets	To treat hair fall and hair growth	Akshay Pharmaceuticals
Histamine	Tablet	To stabilize most cells, relief from sneezing,runny nose and allergies	Kerala Ayurveda Ltd.
Iqwin	Capsule	Anti-stress and to improve memory	SKM Siddha and Ayurveda Company
Kesini Oil	Oil	Treatment of hairfall and dandruff	Kerala Ayurveda Ltd.
Liverson	Tablet	To treat hepatitis and jaundice	Ajmera Pharmaceutical Ltd.
Mentat	Tablet	For memory gain, calmative and brain disease	The Himalaya Drug Company
Ranger	Syrup	Antistress and to improve immunity	Vans health and Pharmaceuticals, Vadodara, Gujarat
Sesa oil	Oil	To nourish hair root, scalp and remove dandruff	Bhanu Labs Pvt .Ltd.

Strensil	Tablet	To treat depression, insomnia	Nagarjuna Ayurvedic Group
Slogo	Capsule	To treat mental stress	Virgo UAP Pharma Ltd.
Sumenta	Tablet	For depression	Character Pharma Ltd.
Stressoneel	Capsule	To treat hypertension stress	Lama company
Kesini oil	Oil	Treatment of hair fall and dandruff	Kerala Ayurveda

PHARMACOLOGY BASED STUDIES OF N.JATAMANSI

Activity	Plant part used	Extracting solvent\Extract	Test system	Used against	Major outcomes
Antidepressant	Root	EtOH	<i>in vivo</i>	Male albino wistar rats	Increase in level of DA, NE, 5HT, 5-HIAA, GABA after 15 days treatment ^[35]
Antifungal	Rhizome	Essential oil	<i>in vivo</i>	Fungal strains: <i>Aspergillus flavus</i> , <i>Furarium oxysporum</i> , <i>Aspergillus niger</i>	Oil effective against one or more moulds ^[36]
Antimicrobial	Root	50% EtOH	<i>in vivo</i>	Bacterial strains: <i>E.coli</i> <i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i> <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> <i>S. typhimurium</i>	Zone of inhibition [diameter] <i>E.coli</i> [21 mm] <i>Klebsiella pneumonia</i> [14mm] <i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> [14mm] <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> [12] <i>S.typhimurium</i> [11mm] ^[37]
Anti-inflammatory	Root	MeOH	<i>in vivo</i>	Female C57BL/6 mice	Reduced endotoxin shock ^[38]
Hepatoprotective	Rhizome	50% EtOH	<i>in vivo</i>	Male wistar rats	Increased survival rate of rat intoxicated with hepatoprotective drug ^[39]
Hepatoprotective	Whole plant	50% EtOH	<i>in vivo</i>	Swiss albino mice	Significant chemoprotective activity of extract in mice ^[40]

Anti Parkinson	Root	EtOH	<i>in vivo</i>	Male wistar rats	Effective for slowing neuronal injury ^[41]
Anticonvulsant	Root	EtOH	<i>in vivo</i>	Male albino wistar rats	Pretreatment of rats with extract plus phenytoin increased protective index of phenytoin ^[42]
Neuroprotective	Root	95% EtOH	<i>in vivo</i>	Male wistar rats	Effective to improve catalase enzyme system, glutamine content and for lipid peroxidation inhibition ^[43]
Anti- diabetic	Whole plant	80% EtOH	<i>in vivo</i>	Alloxan induced male albino rats	High dose of extract exhibited anti-hyperglycemic activity ^[44]
Anti- diabetic	Whole plant	AE	<i>in vivo</i>	Male ICR rats	Extract provided resistance to pancreatic β cell damage ^[45]
Memory improving	Root	95% EtOH	<i>in vivo</i>	Swiss mice model	Effective for learning and as memory restorative agent ^[46]
Antitumor	Root	95% EtOH	<i>in vitro</i>	Human cancer lines Lung cancer [A 549] Liver cancer [HEP 2] Ovary cancer [OVCAR 5] prostate cancer [PC-3]	Alcoholic extracts showed strong <i>in vitro</i> anti- tumour potential. IC ₅₀ = 11.0 mg/mL for HEP-2 IC ₅₀ =17.0 mg/ml for OVCAR-5 ^[47]
Anticancer	Roots and rhizomes	MeOH	<i>In vitro</i>	MCF-7; ER-MDA-MB-231 [Breast carcinoma cells]	Significant anti- cancer potential IC ₅₀ =23.83 mg/mL for MCF-7 IC ₅₀ =58.01 mg/ml for ER-MDA-MB-231 ^[48]

ACUTE TOXICITY STUDIES ^[49]

Acute oral toxicity studies of *N.jatamansi* extracts have been carried-out in Wistar rats following the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) guideline No-423. In reported studies, male rats weighing 150–200 g, after overnight fasting were administered with the plant extract orally up to a dose level of 2000 mg/kg body weight, with free access to water. The animals were observed for signs of toxicity, including behavioural changes, locomotor

activity, convulsions, and mortality up to 72 h post-administration. Body weight changes were also monitored during the observation period. The results indicated that the extracts of *N. jatamansi* did not produce any significant toxic effects or mortality up to the tested dose levels, suggesting a wide margin of safety.

BIOTECHNOLOGICAL APPROACHES FOR CONSERVATION OF *N. JATAMANSI*

Medicinal plants contribute significantly to primary healthcare, cultural heritage, livelihood security and economic development Worldwide (Hamilton, 2004; Moyo et al., 2015). However, most medicinal raw materials are still sourced from the wild, where unscientific and destructive harvesting practices such as uprooting entire plants or removing underground parts before seed set have severely affected natural regeneration (Canter et al., 2005; Rai et al., 2000). As a result, conservation of medicinal plant resources has become a major global challenge due to habitat destruction, over-exploitation and anthropogenic pressures (Hamilton, 2004; Okigbo et al., 2008).

N. jatamansi is extensively used in traditional medicine and commercial herbal formulations, leading to increased demand and unsustainable exploitation of wild populations. Continuous illegal and destructive harvesting has caused a sharp decline in its natural populations, resulting in its classification as a critically endangered species (Ved et al., 2015). Therefore, urgent conservation strategies are required to ensure its survival and to provide authentic plant material for research and pharmaceutical applications.

Conventional propagation methods are limited by poor seed germination and long regeneration periods, making them inefficient for large-scale conservation. In this context, plant biotechnological approaches offer effective alternatives to overcome these constraints (Sarsan et al., 2011; Gandhi et al., 2014). Advances in plant tissue culture techniques have enabled mass propagation, conservation of genetic resources and

reduced pressure on natural habitats (Moyo et al., 2011; Bose et al., 2016; Kumar et al., 2014, 2015). Biotechnological strategies such as *in vitro* micropropagation, somatic embryogenesis, secondary metabolite production and cryopreservation have been explored for the conservation of *N. jatamansi*. Early studies reported shoot regeneration and somatic embryogenesis from callus-derived roots and petiole explants using MS medium supplemented with NAA and kinetin (Mathur, 1992, 1993). However, most protocols showed limited efficiency for multiple shoot induction. An improved micropropagation system using MS medium supplemented with meta-topolin (1.0 mg/L) resulted in a high number of adventitious shoots with good field survival, indicating the potential of optimized *in vitro* systems for large-scale propagation (Bose et al., 2016).

Further refinement of *in vitro* techniques, including cryobanking, synthetic seed technology and bioreactor based scale-up, may support both conservation and commercialization of this high-value medicinal plant. Optimization of explants, culture conditions and plant growth regulators particularly auxins and cytokinins can also enhance biomass accumulation and secondary metabolite production (Amoo et al., 2014; Aremu et al., 2013; Kumar et al., 2019). Alongside biotechnological interventions, implementation of strict conservation policies, sustainable harvesting practices and agroforestry-based domestication strategies is essential for the long-term conservation of *N. jatamansi*.

<i>In vitro</i> studies	Explant type	Optimum concentrations	Major observation	Genetic fidelity Test (Molecular markers used)
In vitro morphogenesis	Callus-derived root	3.0 mg/L	NAA + 0.25 mg/l Kn	None
	Shoot regeneration			
Somatic embryogenesis	Petiole	16.1 mM NAA + 1.16 mM Kn	Somatic embryogenesis	None

Micropropagation	Shoot-tip; Petiole	1.0 mg/L mT	Shoot regeneration	ISJ Total band scored: 63 Monomorphic bands:60 Polymorphic bands:03 SCoT Total band scored: 51 Monomorphic bands:49 Polymorphic bands:02
<i>in vitro</i> regeneration	Leaves	5 mM BA	Callus induction and plant regeneration	RAPD Total band scored: 29 Monomorphic bands:27 Polymorphic bands:02

A model for sustainable utilisation and conservation of *N.jatamansi*

PHARMACOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES OF *N. JATAMANSI*

1. Anti-fungal and Anti-bacterial Activity [50]

N.jatamansi exhibits notable antibacterial and antifungal activity against a wide range of pathogenic microorganisms. This activity is primarily attributed to its essential oil and other bioactive constituents, which inhibit microbial growth by disrupting cell membrane structure and vital metabolic functions. In an antimicrobial screening study involving 61 medicinal plants from 33 families, *N. jatamansi* extract was evaluated using the agar dilution method at concentrations of 500 µg/ml and 1000 µg/ml. The

methanolic extract showed inhibitory effects against *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Candida albicans*, *Streptococcus faecalis*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, and *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, thereby confirming its potential as an effective antibacterial and antifungal agent.

2. Hepatoprotective activity[51]

N.jatamansi has been widely reported to exhibit hepatoprotective potential against liver injury induced by toxic chemicals, alcohol and pharmaceutical agents, thereby supporting normal hepatic function. The plant strengthens endogenous antioxidant mechanisms, mitigates oxidative stress and aids in the repair and regeneration of damaged hepatocytes. Bioactive constituents present in the rhizomes are also

believed to facilitate detoxification pathways. Experimental studies in rats have shown that oral administration of a 50% ethanolic extract of *N.jatamansi* rhizomes at a dose of 800 mg/kg prior to thioacetamide exposure markedly decreased elevated serum markers such as aminotransferases and alkaline phosphatase. The restoration of these altered biochemical parameters confirms the protective effect of the extract against thioacetamide-induced hepatic injury.

3. Cardioprotective activity^[52]

N.jatamansi has been reported to exert cardioprotective effects by supporting normal heart function and reducing the risk of cardiovascular disorders. These effects are mainly associated with its antihypertensive, lipid-lowering and antioxidant properties, which collectively help minimize oxidative damage to cardiac tissue. In an experimental rat model, administration of doxorubicin (15 mg/kg, iply) produced marked myocardial injury, as evidenced by increased serum levels of cardiac marker enzymes such as lactate dehydrogenase, creatine phosphokinase, aspartate aminotransferase and alanine aminotransferase. Doxorubicin treatment also caused significant disturbances in endogenous antioxidant defence systems, including reduced activities of superoxide dismutase, glutathione peroxidase, catalase and glutathione-S-transferase, along with enhanced lipid peroxidation. Pre-treatment with *N.jatamansi* extract effectively attenuated these alterations, restoring antioxidant enzyme activities and lipid peroxide levels close to normal values, thereby demonstrating its cardioprotective potential.

4. Hypolipidimic activity^[53]

N.jatamansi has been reported to exhibit hypolipidemic activity by reducing elevated levels of blood lipids, particularly cholesterol and triglycerides, thereby lowering the risk of

cardiovascular complications. This effect is primarily attributed to its regulatory influence on hepatic enzymes involved in lipid synthesis and degradation. In an experimental study, rats receiving a single intraperitoneal injection of doxorubicin (15 mg/kg) showed significant increases in serum and myocardial lipid components, including cholesterol, triglycerides, free fatty acids and phospholipids. Additionally, doxorubicin administration led to elevated serum levels of low-density and very low-density lipoproteins (LDL and VLDL), accompanied by a reduction in high-density lipoproteins (HDL), indicating disrupted lipid homeostasis and altered lipid-metabolizing enzyme activity in both serum and cardiac tissues. Pre-treatment with *N.jatamansi* extract at an oral dose of 500 mg/kg for seven consecutive days prior to doxorubicin exposure significantly normalized lipid profiles and restored the activity of lipid-metabolizing enzymes. These biochemical improvements were further supported by histopathological findings, confirming the protective role of the extract.

5. Antidepressant activity [54]

N.jatamansi has been suggested as a potential supportive therapy for affective disorders, including depression and anxiety. Its therapeutic action is believed to involve the regulation of key neurotransmitters such as serotonin and dopamine, thereby exerting a calming effect on the central nervous system and improving emotional balance. The antidepressant potential of the methanolic extract of *N. jatamansi* was assessed in inbred male Swiss mice using standard behavioural models, namely the forced swim test (FST), tail suspension test (TST) and locomotor activity evaluation. Oral administration of the extract at doses of 200 and 400 mg/kg was compared with the reference antidepressant imipramine (10 mg/kg, orally) in both normal and sleep-deprived animals. The extract demonstrated a statistically

significant antidepressant-like effect ($P < 0.001$) in both FST and TST at both dose levels, with efficacy comparable to imipramine. Locomotor performance remained unaffected in normal mice; however, in sleep-deprived mice, treatment with the extract significantly enhanced locomotor activity ($P < 0.01$), restoring it toward normal levels. These observations indicate a dose-dependent antidepressant effect of *N.jatamansi* and highlight its potential usefulness in managing depression associated with sleep deprivation.

6. Antioxidant, Neuroprotective and Anti-stress activities: [55]

N.jatamansi exhibits potent antioxidant properties that protect cellular components from oxidative injury and contribute to neuroprotection and stress reduction. The therapeutic effects are primarily mediated through bioactive constituents capable of neutralizing free radicals, thereby limiting oxidative damage that is closely associated with cognitive decline and neurodegenerative conditions. The anti-stress potential of a hydro-ethanolic extract of *N. jatamansi* was investigated in correlation with its antioxidant activity using a restraint stress model in Wistar rats. Animals were allocated into four groups: normal (naïve), stress control and two treatment groups receiving oral doses of 200 mg/kg (T-200) and 500 mg/kg (T-500) of the extract prior to stress exposure. Stress was induced by subjecting the rats to restraint in metallic chambers at 4°C for 4 h followed by evaluation of stress-related biochemical changes and gastric ulcer formation. *In vitro* assays confirmed the free radical scavenging capacity of the extract. Pre-treatment with *N.jatamansi* significantly attenuated stress-induced elevations in lipid peroxidation and nitric oxide levels and restored reduced catalase activity in brain tissue. These results collectively demonstrate the pronounced anti-stress and neuroprotective effects

of *N.jatamansi*, largely mediated through its antioxidant mechanisms.

7. Antiparkinson activity[56]

N.jatamansi has been explored for its potential role in the management of Parkinson's disease, particularly due to its ability to mitigate motor impairments such as tremors and muscle rigidity. The neuroprotective effect of the plant is primarily attributed to its capacity to preserve dopaminergic neurons and counteract oxidative damage within the brain, thereby supporting motor coordination and neurological function. In an experimental model, rats were orally administered with root extracts of *N.jatamansi* at doses of 200, 400 and 600 mg/kg body weight for a period of three weeks. On the 21st day, Parkinsonian symptoms were induced by stereotaxic infusion of 6-hydroxydopamine (6-OHDA; 12 mg dissolved in 0.01% Ascorbic acid-saline) into the right striatum, while control animals received vehicle alone. Behavioural assessments conducted three weeks after lesion induction revealed significant impairments in locomotion, muscle coordination and drug-induced rotational behaviour. Biochemical and neurochemical evaluations performed 6 weeks later showed increased lipid peroxidation, depletion of reduced glutathione and altered activities of antioxidant enzymes, along with changes in catecholamine levels, dopamine-D₂ receptor binding and tyrosine hydroxylase expression. Treatment with *N.jatamansi* extract produced a dose-dependent reversal of these behavioural and biochemical abnormalities, indicating its neuroprotective and anti-Parkinsonian potential.

8. Anticonvulsant activity[57]

N.jatamansi has attracted attention for its potential anticonvulsant properties and its ability to alleviate seizure activity. The therapeutic effect is believed to arise from modulation of neurotransmitter signalling and reinforcement of inhibitory neural

mechanisms, thereby reducing abnormal neuronal firing. The anticonvulsant efficacy of an ethanolic extract of roots of *N.jatamansi* was investigated using established experimental models. The extract produced a marked elevation in seizure threshold in the maximal electroshock seizure (MES) model, as reflected by a reduction in the extension to flexion ratio, whereas no significant protection was observed against pentylenetetrazole induced convulsions. Additionally, combined administration of *N.jatamansi* extract (50 mg/kg) with phenytoin at doses ranging from 12.5 to 75 mg/kg significantly enhanced the protective index of phenytoin, increasing it from 3.62 to 13.17. Dose-dependent studies further demonstrated that both phenytoin alone and its combination with the plant extract influenced serum phenytoin concentrations, confirming a synergistic interaction between the two treatments.

9. Antihyperglycemic effect[58]

N.jatamansi (spikenard) has been reported to exhibit antihyperglycemic potential, suggesting its usefulness in the management of diabetes mellitus. The antidiabetic effect is mediated through multiple mechanisms, including improvement of insulin sensitivity, enhanced peripheral glucose utilization and suppression of hepatic gluconeogenesis, thereby contributing to better glycaemic control. In an experimental study, rats treated with *N.jatamansi* root extract at doses of 200, 800, and 1200 mg/kg for 10 days demonstrated a dose-dependent reduction in blood glucose levels. Among the tested doses, 1200 mg/kg produced a significant antihyperglycemic effect when compared with diabetic control animals. Toxicological evaluation further indicated the absence of adverse effects even at a higher dose of 2000 mg/kg, highlighting the extract's wide margin of safety. These results support the potential of *N. jatamansi* as a safe

adjunctive agent in the management of hyperglycemia.

10.Effect on Estrogen and Hair growth[59]

N.jatamansi may promote hair growth by influencing hormonal balance, especially estrogen levels. It is believed that the herb stimulates hair follicles and extends the active growth phase (anagen) by interacting with estrogen receptors. Studies on *N.jatamansi* root extract have demonstrated its hair growth promotion activities, particularly in the context of hair loss resulting from cancer treatments

11. Nootropic activity

N.jatamansi has been reported to possess nootropic potential by enhancing learning, memory, and overall cognitive performance, thereby contributing to improved brain function. These effects are thought to result from improved cerebral circulation and increased neuronal plasticity. Experimental studies conducted in young and aged mice demonstrated that oral administration of *N. jatamansi* root extract at doses of 50, 100, and 200 mg/kg for 7 consecutive days produced a dose-dependent improvement in cognitive function. Among the tested doses, 200 mg/kg significantly enhanced learning and memory in young mice. Furthermore, the same dose effectively attenuated memory impairment induced by diazepam (1 mg/kg, iply) and scopolamine (0.4 mg/kg), indicating its protective effect against drug-induced amnesia.

12. Anticancer Activity

Preliminary investigations indicate that *N.jatamansi* possesses potential anticancer properties by inhibiting the proliferation of malignant cells. The anticancer mechanism is thought to involve induction of programmed cell death (apoptosis) and suppression of tumour cell growth, largely attributed to the presence of bioactive phytoconstituents. *In vitro* studies using

N.jatamansi root extract at concentrations of 30 mg/ml and 100 mg/ml demonstrated significant antiproliferative activity against human neuroblastoma cell lines. The extract produced growth inhibition of 54% and 91% in IMR-32 cells and 45% and 82% in SKN-SH cells respectively, as determined by the Sulforhodamine B (SRB) assay

13. Radioprotective activity[60]

N.jatamansi has been reported to exhibit radioprotective potential, primarily due to its strong antioxidant activity, which may help mitigate radiation-induced cellular injury. The protective effect is attributed to the scavenging of free radicals generated during radiation exposure, thereby limiting oxidative damage to tissues. In an experimental study, Swiss albino mice were exposed to 6 Gy of Electron Beam Radiation (EBR) to evaluate the radioprotective efficacy of *N. jatamansi* root extract. A survival analysis was conducted to determine the lethal dose parameters and the dose reduction factor (DRF) of the extract was calculated by comparing the LD₅₀ values of EBR in treated and untreated animals. The observed increase in LD₅₀ in extract-treated mice confirmed the radioprotective effect of *N.jatamansi*.

14. Anticataleptic activity[59]

The hydroalcoholic root extract of *N. jatamansi* was evaluated for its antioxidant and anticataleptic activities using a haloperidol-induced catalepsy model in rats. Catalepsy was induced in male Wistar rats by intraperitoneal administration of haloperidol (1 mg/kg). Behavioural assessments, biochemical parameters and neurotransmitter levels were analysed. All extract-treated groups showed a significant reduction in cataleptic scores ($P < 0.01$) compared with the haloperidol-treated group with the greatest effect observed at a dose of 500 mg/kg body weight of *N.jatamansi*.

15. Tranquilizing activity [60]

German *et al.* investigated the tranquilizing activity of the sesquiterpene **valeranone (jatamansone)** isolated from the rhizomes of *N.jatamansi* DC. In rodent models, valeranone produced a significant prolongation of barbiturate-induced hypnosis and caused impairment of Rotarod performance, indicating central nervous system depressant activity. Additionally, the compound exhibited hypotensive effects, further supporting its tranquilizing potential.

16. Effect on Autism disease [61]

This plant exhibits calming and sedative properties that help regulate nervous system activity. By promoting neural relaxation, it supports better sleep patterns and reduces behavioural symptoms such as anxiety, irritability and restlessness. These effects may be beneficial in neurological conditions, including autism spectrum disorders, where heightened excitability and sleep disturbances are commonly observed.

THERAPEUTIC BENEFITS OF JATAMANSI (*N. JATAMANSI*)

1. Hair health:

Jatamansi is widely used for maintaining healthy hair. It supports hair growth by enhancing blood circulation to the scalp and strengthening hair follicles, thereby reducing hair fall. The herb also helps manage dandruff, minimizes hair breakage and improves overall hair texture. These benefits can be achieved through topical application of jatamansi oil, use of powdered rhizome in hair masks or oral consumption as per traditional practices.

2. Brain health:

Jatamansi is valued for its neuroprotective and calming effects on the central nervous system. Traditionally, it has been used as a brain tonic to

enhance memory, concentration and cognitive function. It is also known to reduce anxiety and depressive symptoms and has been included as an ingredient in classical Ayurvedic formulations such as *Saraswatarishta*, which are used to promote mental well-being.

3. Skin health:

The herb is traditionally employed in skin care due to its anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties. Jatamansi may help reduce acne, soothe irritated skin and protect against oxidative damage. Its regular use is also associated with improved skin texture and a reduction in fine lines and wrinkles, contributing to anti-aging effects.

4. Promotion of sleep and management of insomnia:

Jatamansi is commonly used to improve sleep quality and manage insomnia. Its calming action on the nervous system helps induce relaxation, making it beneficial for individuals experiencing sleep disturbances and stress-related insomnia.

5. Reduction of inflammation and pain:

Owing to its anti-inflammatory and analgesic properties, Jatamansi has been traditionally used to alleviate pain and inflammation. It may be beneficial in conditions such as arthritis, gout and other inflammatory disorders.

5. Cardiovascular health:

Jatamansi has been reported to possess cardioprotective properties. Traditional use suggests its role in regulating blood pressure, improving blood circulation and supporting overall heart health, thereby potentially reducing the risk of cardiovascular disorders.

7. Digestive health:

The plant has been traditionally used to support digestive function and relieve gastrointestinal complaints such as indigestion, bloating and

constipation. Its carminative and digestive properties aid in stimulating digestion and reducing inflammation within the gastrointestinal tract.

8. Liver health and detoxification:

Jatamansi is known for its hepatoprotective activity and has been used to promote liver health. It may help protect liver cells from damage and enhance the liver's natural detoxification processes.

9. Air purification and calming of the environment:

Beyond its medicinal uses, Jatamansi holds spiritual significance in traditional practices. Burning jatamansi as incense is believed to purify the surrounding air and create a peaceful, calming atmosphere. It has long been used during meditation, yoga and religious rituals and is often referred to as a "spiritual herb" for its ability to promote mental tranquillity and spiritual focus.

POTENTIAL SIDE EFFECTS AND PRECAUTIONS ASSOCIATED WITH JATAMANSI USE

1. Jatamansi is generally considered safe when consumed within the prescribed or recommended dosage range. However, intake in excessive amounts may lead to adverse effects such as dizziness, headache, nausea or dryness of the mouth.
2. The use of Jatamansi during pregnancy and lactation is not advised, as adequate scientific evidence regarding its safety during these stages is lacking.
3. Jatamansi may influence the action of certain medications, particularly antiplatelet agents, antihypertensive drugs and central nervous system depressants. Hence, medical consultation is recommended before its use along with other medications.

4. Individuals with bleeding disorders or those undergoing surgical procedures should refrain from using Jatamansi, as it may increase the tendency for bleeding.

CONCLUSION

N.jatamansi DC. is a valuable medicinal plant with well-documented traditional significance and growing scientific validation. Botanical and pharmacognostical studies support its proper identification and quality assessment, while phytochemical investigations reveal the presence of bioactive constituents responsible for its diverse pharmacological activities, particularly in neurological and antioxidant related disorders. Experimental studies substantiate many traditional claims and indicate a favourable safety profile at therapeutic doses; however, the lack of extensive clinical evaluation and standardized formulations remains a limitation. Additionally, over exploitation has rendered the plant endangered, highlighting the need for effective conservation strategies. Therefore, further clinical research, standardization and biotechnological conservation approaches are essential to ensure the safe, effective and sustainable utilization of *N. jatamansi* in future herbal drug development.

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